

April 2015

From researchers to national plant protection organisations: Euphresco-EPPO relationship

Since April 1 2014, the coordination of Euphresco is hosted within the European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization. The advantages of this are multiple: Euphresco enjoys of an international exposure, and this is fundamental in view of an enlargement of the current Network. Also very important, any information produced by Euphresco and through Euphresco could be disseminated in the EPPO region and abroad. Finally, **the outputs of research projects funded through Euphresco provide valuable support for the development of EPPO Standards, supporting the daily work of national plant protection organisations (NPPOs). Below it is a list of Euphresco projects that have been used, are currently used or are planned to be used to support the EPPO diagnostic activity. The list of EPPO Diagnostic Protocols can be found [here](#)**

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- 'Development and validation of innovative diagnostic tools for the detection of fire blight (*Erwinia amylovora*)' has been used for the revision of PM 7/20
- 'Development and validation of diagnostic methods for *Gibberella circinata* (*Fusarium circinatum*) cause of pitch pine canker' has been used for the development of PM 7/91
- 'Phytosanitary diagnostic, on-site detection and epidemiology tools for fire blight' has been used for the revision of PM 7/20

The following projects are currently used:

- 'Detection and epidemiology of *Pospiviroids*', used for the development of generic Standard on Pospiviroid detection
- 'Assessment of the risk posed by ornamentals and tomato seeds infected by *Pospiviroids* to tomato crops and evaluation of *Pospiviroid* detection protocols for seed testing in tomato', used for the revision of PM 7/33 on *Potato spindle tuber viroid*
- 'Ring testing of diagnostic methods for the identification of potato cyst nematodes (*Globodera rostochiensis* and *G. pallida*)', used for the revision of PM 7/40
- 'Ring test on diagnostic methods for *Pantoea stewartii* ssp. *stewartii*, maize bacterial blight', used for the development of PM 7/60
- 'Interlaboratory tests for the detection of *Clavibacter michiganensis* ssp. *sepedonicus* (potato ring rot) and *Ralstonia solanacearum* (potato brown rot)', used for the revision of PM 7/59 and PM 7/21

- 'Detection and management of the quarantine nematodes *Meloidogyne chitwoodi* and *Meloidogyne fallax*', used for the revision of PM 7/41
- 'Interlaboratory comparison and validation of detection methods for phytoplasmas of phytosanitary concern in European orchards', used for the revision of PM 7/62 on *Candidatus Phytoplasma mali* and PM 7/63 on *Candidatus Phytoplasma pyri*
- 'Development of pathotype-specific PCR tests for the identification of *Synchytrium endobioticum* pathotype 1', used for the revision of PM 7/28
- 'Diagnostic methods for *Synchytrium endobioticum*, especially for pathotype identification', used for the revision of PM 7/28
- 'Development and validation of innovative diagnostic tools for detection and identification of *Meloidogyne enterolobii* in support of integrated plant protection strategies', used for the development of PM 7/103
- 'Epidemiology and diagnosis of potato phytoplasmas and *Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum* and their contribution to risk management', used for the development of a new PM 7 on *Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum*
- 'Epidemiological studies on reservoir hosts and potential vectors of Grapevine flavescence dorée (GFD) and validation of different diagnostic procedures for GFD', used for the revision of PM 7/79

In future months, the following projects will also support EPPO work:

- 'Determination of specificity and test performance study of current and novel molecular methods for *Ralstonia solanacearum* (brown rot of potatoes) and identification of methods allowing for detection of non-European strains of brown rot' (will be used for the revision of PM 7/21)
- 'Diagnostics and risk management for plant health threats in wood chips and bark for bio-energy imported from other continents'
- 'Epitrix (flea beetle) species, life cycles and detection method' (will be used for the revision of PM 7/109)
- 'Grapevine flavescence doreé (FD) follow up Vitisens, GRAFDEPI and Qdetect' (will be used for the revision of PM 7/79)
- '*Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *actinidiae* (PSA): diagnosis, detection, identification and study of epidemiological aspects' (will be used for the revision of PM 7/120)
- 'Reference collection for regulated viruses and viroids'
- 'Update and validation of DNA Barcoding protocols by end-users' (used in the development of a generic Standard on DNA barcoding as identification tool for some regulated plant pests)
- 'Rapid diagnostics of *Xanthomonas arboricola* pv. *pruni* (Xap): development and validation of methodologies for discrimination between Xap isolates and look-a-likes' is used for the revision of PM 7/64